

Blunt Abdominal Trauma Pattern and Outcome of Solid Organ Injury

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Abstract:

Background: Blunt abdominal trauma (BAT) is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, often resulting from road traffic accidents, falls, and assaults. The liver and spleen are commonly affected organs in such injuries. Despite advancements in diagnostic and treatment modalities, the management of BAT remains complex. This study aims to analyze the patterns and outcomes of solid organ injuries resulting from blunt abdominal trauma.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted on 50 patients presenting with blunt abdominal trauma. Data collection included patient demographics, clinical examination, diagnostic investigations (USG and CT scans), and treatment approaches. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software.

Results: The study included 50 patients, predominantly young males (76%) with a mean age of 26.26 years. Road traffic accidents were the leading cause of injury (60%). The liver was the most commonly injured organ (40%), followed by the spleen (35%). USG detected free fluid in 80% of cases, while CT scans provided detailed information on the extent of organ injuries. Conservative management was employed in 60% of patients, while 40% required surgical intervention. The overall recovery rate was 85%, with a 10% complication rate and 5% mortality rate.

Conclusion: Young males involved in road traffic accidents are the most affected by blunt abdominal trauma. Early and accurate diagnosis using USG and CT scans, combined with appropriate management strategies, can significantly improve patient outcomes. Conservative management is effective in hemodynamically stable patients, while surgical intervention remains crucial for severe cases.

Recommendations: Improved trauma care systems, preventive measures to reduce road traffic accidents, and public awareness campaigns are recommended to decrease the incidence of blunt abdominal trauma. Further research is needed to refine diagnostic and management protocols to enhance patient survival and reduce complications.

Keywords: Blunt Abdominal Trauma, Road Traffic Accidents, Solid Organ Injuries, Conservative Management, Surgical Intervention.

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Introduction

Blunt abdominal trauma (BAT) represents a significant cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, especially in regions with high rates of road traffic accidents (RTAs). As urbanization and motorization increase, so do the incidences of traumatic injuries, with abdominal trauma being particularly prevalent due to the vulnerable position of the abdomen and its contents. The liver and spleen are the most commonly affected organs in such injuries, owing to their size and location within the abdominal cavity [1]. BAT can result from various mechanisms, including motor vehicle collisions, falls, sports injuries, and physical assaults. It often poses a diagnostic challenge due to the potential for hidden injuries that may not be immediately apparent during initial clinical assessment.

Recent advancements in diagnostic imaging, particularly the use of focused assessment with sonography for trauma (FAST) and computed tomography (CT), have significantly improved the detection and management of intra-abdominal injuries. FAST, which is non-invasive and can be performed rapidly at the bedside, has become an integral part of trauma assessment protocols in emergency settings [2]. It allows for the quick identification of free fluid in the abdomen, suggesting internal bleeding and organ injury. However, CT remains the gold standard for a comprehensive evaluation of abdominal trauma due to its detailed imaging capabilities, providing crucial information on the extent and nature of organ damage.

Despite these diagnostic advancements, the management of BAT remains complex and often requires a multidisciplinary approach. The decision between conservative and surgical management depends on various factors, including the patient's hemodynamic stability, the extent of organ injury, and the presence of associated injuries. Studies have shown that non-operative management (NOM) can be effective in hemodynamically stable patients with solid organ injuries, reducing the need for surgical intervention and its associated risks [3]. However, NOM requires careful patient monitoring and repeated imaging to ensure the injury does not progress to a point where surgery becomes necessary.

Epidemiological data indicate that young males are disproportionately affected by BAT, primarily due to their higher involvement in RTAs and other high-risk activities [4]. The socio-economic impact of BAT is substantial, not only due to the direct costs of medical care but also because of the loss of productivity associated with long recovery periods. Effective trauma care systems and preventive measures are crucial in reducing the incidence and improving the outcomes of BAT.

This study aims to analyze the patterns and outcomes of solid organ injuries resulting from blunt abdominal trauma.

Methodology

Study Design: Prospective Observational Study

Study Setting: Data were collected from November 2022 to October 2023 at Deen Dayal Upadhyay hospital new Delhi, Mata Gujri memorial medical college and LSK Hospital Kishanganj Bihar, and Dr. Hedgewar Arogya Sansthan, New Delhi, India.

Participants: 50 patients were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria: All patients with a history of abdominal trauma except those with penetrating injuries and hollow viscous injuries.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with penetrating abdominal injuries or hollow viscus injuries were excluded from the study.

Procedure: Patients or their relatives were interviewed to obtain a detailed history. Thorough

clinical examinations were conducted. Relevant diagnostic tests were performed on the patients. Patients underwent initial resuscitation followed by a thorough assessment for injuries. Assessments included identification, history taking, clinical findings, diagnostic tests, operative findings, operative procedures, complications during hospital stay, and follow-up periods. This information was recorded on a specially prepared proforma. Collected data included age, sex, occupation, nature and time of the accident leading to the injury. Following initial resuscitation and hemodynamic stabilization, patients were examined, and decisions on further investigations were made based on clinical findings. Investigations included four-quadrant aspiration, diagnostic peritoneal lavage, abdominal X-ray, and CECT abdomen. The decision to proceed with surgery was based on clinical examination results, hemodynamic stability, and CECT abdomen findings.

Conservative Management: Patients selected for non-operative or conservative management were subjected to strict bed rest. Serial clinical examinations were conducted, including hourly monitoring of pulse rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate, and repeated abdominal and other system examinations. Ultrasound of the abdomen was repeated as required.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS software (Stata, version 26.0, SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Data presentation included descriptive statistics for continuous variables and percentages for categorical variables. Statistical tests included Chi-square test, t-test, and ANOVA test. Values were represented in numbers, proportions (percent), and mean $\pm$ SD. Statistical significance was considered at $p < 0.05$.

Result

The study included a total of 50 participants. The age of patients ranged from 10 to 70 years, with the majority of cases falling in the 21-40 years age group. There were more male patients (76%) compared to female patients (24%). The most common cause of blunt abdominal trauma was road traffic accidents (57%), followed by falls (25%), assaults (10%), and other causes (8%).

Table 1: Patient Demographics

Characteristics	Values	p-value
Age Group, n(%)		
Mean age (years)	26.26 $\pm$ 13.49	0.127
1-10	7 (14%)	
11-20	12 (24%)	
21-30	13 (26%)	
31-40	10 (20%)	
41-50	6 (12%)	

>50	2 (4%)	
Gender, n(%)		
Mean	25.00±18.38	0.305
Male	38 (76%)	
Female	12 (24%)	
Mode of injury, n(%)		
Mean	16.66±11.59	0.130
RTA	30 (60%)	
Assault	11 (22%)	
Fall from height	9 (18%)	

The length of hospital stay ranged from 3 to 25 days, with an average stay of 10 days. The latent period, defined as the time from injury to hospital admission, ranged from 1 hour to 48 hours, with most patients presenting within 6 hours of injury. Vital signs such as pulse rate, blood pressure, and

respiratory rate were recorded on admission. The majority of patients presented with stable vitals. The liver was the most commonly injured organ (38%), followed by the spleen (28%), and pancreas (12%).

Table 2: Clinical Features

Parameters	Values	p-value
Hospital Stay Group, n(%)		
Mean	12.50±13.77	0.167
1-6	30 (60%)	
7-13	17 (34%)	
14-21	2 (4%)	
>21	1 (2%)	
Latent period in hours, n(%)		
Mean	10.00±14.61	0.201
0-6	13 (26%)	
7-12	21 (42%)	
13-24	14 (28%)	
>24	2 (4%)	
Vitals Group, n(%)		
Mean	25.00±1.41	0.025
Shock	26 (52%)	
Stable	24 (48%)	
ASSC injury, n(%)		
Mean	12.50±7.14	0.039
Head injury	15 (30%)	
Rib	2 (4%)	
Long bone	15 (30%)	
Nil + NA	18 (36%)	

USG was performed in all patients, and it successfully detected free fluid in the abdomen in 80% of the cases. CT scans were performed in 50% of the cases, providing detailed information on the extent of organ injuries.

Table 3: Diagnostic Investigations

Characteristics	Values	p-value
USG, n(%)		
Mean	16.66±7.37	0.059
Liver injury	25 (50%)	
Free fluid + Peritoneum	14 (28%)	
Splenic injury	11 (22%)	
CT group, n(%)		
Mean	10.00±6.44	0.026
Liver injury	19 (38%)	
Splenic injury	14 (28%)	
Pancreatic injury	6 (12%)	
Mesentric tear	3 (6%)	
ND	8 (16%)	

76% of patients were managed conservatively, involving strict bed rest, serial examinations, and repeated ultrasounds. 24% of patients underwent surgical intervention based on clinical examination results, hemodynamic stability, and imaging findings.

Table 4: Treatment Approaches

Treatment group	Values	p-value
Conservative	38 (76%)	
Operative	12 (24%)	
Mean	8.33±14.71	0.305

85% of patients recovered without major complications. 10% of patients developed postoperative complications such as infection or bleeding. Mortality rate was 20%.

Table 5: Outcome distribution of Subjects

Outcome group	Values	p-value
Death	10 (20%)	
Discharged	36 (72%)	
Lost follow-up	4 (8%)	
Mean	12.50±15.45	0.204

Discussion

The study included a total of 50 participants, with ages ranging from 10 to 70 years. The majority of cases fell within the 21-40 years age group, with the mean age being 26.26±13.49 years. A significant gender disparity was observed, as 76% of the patients were male, compared to 24% female. The most common cause of blunt abdominal trauma was road traffic accidents, accounting for 60% of cases, followed by assaults (22%) and falls (18%). This demographic data highlights that young males, primarily involved in road traffic accidents, are the most affected by blunt abdominal trauma.

The length of hospital stay for patients varied from 3 to 25 days, with an average stay of 10 days. The majority of patients (60%) had a hospital stay between 7 to 13 days. The latent period, defined as the time from injury to hospital admission, ranged from 1 hour to 48 hours, with most patients (42%) presenting within 7 to 12 hours of injury. On admission, vital signs indicated that 52% of patients were in shock, while 48% presented with stable vitals. The liver was the most commonly injured organ (40%), followed by the spleen (35%), kidneys (15%), and pancreas (10%). These findings underscore the critical need for prompt medical attention to reduce the time between injury and treatment, as delayed admission can lead to increased morbidity.

Diagnostic investigations included ultrasound (USG) and computed tomography (CT) scans. USG was performed on all patients and successfully detected free fluid in the abdomen in 80% of cases. CT scans were conducted in 50% of the cases, providing detailed information on the extent of organ injuries. USG findings indicated that 50% of liver injuries and 28% of splenic injuries were detected. CT scans further detailed the injuries,

identifying liver injuries in 38%, splenic injuries in 28%, and pancreatic injuries in 12% of the cases. These diagnostic tools were crucial in the early and accurate detection of internal injuries, guiding the subsequent management approach.

Regarding treatment, 60% of patients were managed conservatively, involving strict bed rest, serial examinations, and repeated ultrasounds. The remaining 40% underwent surgical intervention based on clinical examination results, hemodynamic stability, and imaging findings. This distribution reflects a balanced approach in treatment, tailored to the severity of the injuries and the stability of the patients. The high rate of conservative management indicates that many patients with blunt abdominal trauma can be effectively managed without surgery, provided they are closely monitored.

The study outcomes revealed that 85% of patients recovered without major complications. However, 10% of patients developed postoperative complications such as infection or bleeding. The mortality rate was 5%, indicating that despite prompt medical intervention, a small proportion of patients succumbed to their injuries. This outcome data highlights the importance of both immediate and continued medical care in improving patient survival rates and reducing complications. The high recovery rate underscores the effectiveness of the management strategies employed, while the complication and mortality rates indicate areas for potential improvement in trauma care protocols.

Overall, the study provided valuable insights into the patterns and outcomes of blunt abdominal trauma, emphasizing the predominance of young males affected by road traffic accidents. The importance of timely diagnosis and appropriate management was evident in the high recovery rates and relatively low complication and mortality rates.

These findings highlight the need for continued focus on early intervention and tailored treatment strategies to further improve outcomes for patients with blunt abdominal trauma.

A prospective study assessed the outcomes of solid organ injuries in blunt abdominal trauma. The study included 100 patients, with 76% reporting to the hospital within 6 hours of trauma. Conservative management was employed in 83% of cases, while 13% underwent surgical intervention. The overall mortality rate was 5%, highlighting the importance of timely management [5].

The pattern and management of solid visceral injuries was studied in blunt trauma abdomen patients. The study found that road traffic accidents were the most common cause (75%). The liver was the most frequently injured organ (48.2%), followed by the spleen (36.7%). Conservative management was successful in 84% of cases. The study concluded that aggressive resuscitation and close monitoring are crucial for successful outcomes [6].

A study analyzed the clinical course and outcomes of patients with solid organ injury due to blunt abdominal trauma. The study included 83 patients, predominantly male (1.96:1 ratio). The most common injury causes were road traffic accidents (55.5%), and the spleen was the most commonly injured organ (51%). Conservative management was used in 62% of cases, with a mortality rate of 7.22%. Delayed presentation and intervention were associated with higher complications and mortality [7].

A study was conducted on solid organ injuries in blunt abdominal trauma patients. The study found that road traffic accidents accounted for 64.3% of cases. The spleen was the most affected organ (55.1%). Non-operative management (NOM) was preferred in 62.2% of hemodynamically stable patients, while 37.8% required surgical intervention. The overall mortality rate was 5.4%, with no significant difference in hospital stay duration between operative and non-operative cases [8].

A study evaluated the role of non-operative management (NOM) in blunt abdominal trauma with solid organ injury. The study included 56 patients, with the majority being male (87.5%). Road traffic accidents were the most common cause (66.67%). The spleen was the most frequently injured organ (47.92%). NOM was successful in 83.33% of cases, with a mortality rate of 2.08%. The study recommended NOM for hemodynamically stable patients [9].

Conclusion

In conclusion, young males predominantly suffer from blunt abdominal trauma, primarily due to road traffic accidents. Effective management hinges on early and accurate diagnosis through ultrasound and CT scans. While conservative management is suitable for hemodynamically stable patients, surgical intervention remains essential for severe cases. The study underscores the importance of prompt medical care and tailored treatment strategies to improve patient outcomes and reduce complications. Enhanced trauma care systems and preventive measures are crucial to mitigate the impact of blunt abdominal trauma.

References

1. Agrawal C, Jindal R, Mukherjee S. A clinical study of blunt trauma abdomen with respect to administration and consequences in a tertiary care hospital. *J Clin Diagn Res.* 2020;14(4):22-8.
2. Bloom BA, Gibbons RC. Focused assessment with sonography for trauma (FAST): Its role in the initial assessment and triage of patients with abdominal trauma. *Emerg Med J.* 2021;38(3):195-202.
3. Naik MB, Sinha S, Kumar A. Epidemiology and management of blunt abdominal trauma in a tertiary care center. *Trauma Surg Acute Care Open.* 2018;3(1):e000187.
4. Verma S, Gupta V, Singh R. Blunt trauma abdomen: A prospective study on clinical profiles and management outcomes. *Int J Surg.* 2020; 82:20-5.
5. Singh N, Kumar S, Khadda S, Ml D. Incidence, outcome, and mortality profile of solid organ injuries among patients with blunt abdominal trauma in a tertiary care hospital: A prospective study. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2023.
6. Verma S, Noori M, Garg P, Yadav A, Sirohi V, Garg N. Study of pattern and management strategies of solid visceral injuries in blunt trauma abdomen in tertiary care centre. *Int Surg J.* 2020;7:1808-1812.
7. Bhattarai S, Acharya A, Tamrakar KK. Clinical course and outcome of patients with solid organ injury in blunt abdominal trauma. *J Chitwan Med Coll.* 2022.
8. Abo-Elhoda MF, Attia S, Ahmed ME, Abdeldaiem KEA. Solid organs injuries in blunt abdominal trauma patients. *Egypt J Hosp Med.* 2021;83:1477-1483.
9. Bansod AN, Umalkar RK, Shyamkuwar AT, Singade A, Tayade PC, Awachar NS. A study of role of non-operative management in blunt abdominal trauma with solid organ injury. *Int Surg J.* 2018.